

Translating the intangible: The role of artificial intelligence in the translation of metaphors in tourism discourse

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The application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools is having a profound impact on many areas of our lives. This article focuses on communication, an area that cuts across disciplines and professions and is crucial for the promotion of tourism destinations. More specifically, this study explores the opportunities that AI offers in the translation of metaphors in tourism discourse, where they convey cultural and emotional meanings and are crucial for appealing to international audiences. This study builds on previous research (Spinzi, 2024) on the translation of metaphors in sustainable tourism discourse and aims to explore AI tools, specifically neural machine translation (NMT) systems, for their translation, with particular reference to GPT-4, the most advanced iteration of GPT. It evaluates AI-driven metaphor translation, its efficiency compared to human translators, and examines its impact on intercultural communication in the tourism sector.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Automatic Translation; Metaphors; Tourism Discourse Translation

1. Introduction

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) is having a major impact on many sectors of the economy, not least the creative industries. As it has been noticed (Gretzel et al. 2015), AI has revolutionised the tourism sector by providing innovative solutions for customised tourism experiences, automating customer service and improving global communication. One of the key aspects enabling these advances is particularly evident in the translation industry where AI has proven to be a transformative force, providing automated, efficient and cost-effective solutions to overcome language barriers and improve cross-cultural communication (Mohamed et al. 2024; Pessach & Shmueli, 2022; Zakraoui et al. 2020). The integration of AI, the tourism industry, and translation represent a dynamic frontier in modern technological and cultural exchange.

AI technologies such as Large Language Models (LLMs) have innovated cultural exchange at a deeper level. In particular, LLMs have recently been introduced in the scientific industry to process and interpret vast amounts of textual information. Indeed, LLMs serve as an important tool for researchers (Evans & Patel, 2020), who have confirmed that these models enable scientists to gain

further insights into previously unexplored topics. One of the fascinating aspects of LLMs is that they can act as virtual assistants capable of converting spoken or written languages into complex programming languages such as Java or Python. As Jones (2023) puts it, this has enabled a wide range of students and academic researchers to gain a level of computer literacy similar to that of trained computer professionals (Khan & Ali, 2019).

Nor is academia the only beneficiary of these advances. AI's ability to anticipate consumer activity, optimise the allocation of resources, and generate personalised content for different individuals is, at its core, enabling the travel and tourism industry to advance (Neuhofer et al. 2015). Travelers from diverse backgrounds also benefit from AI-powered translation tools such as machine translation systems with automatic speech recognition, which enable a better understanding of the host country's culture and thus improve access and inclusion. However, while this expansion of AI and automatic translation promotes understanding of people from different cultural backgrounds, it raises significant concerns about accuracy, ethics and cultural impact, especially in areas such as tourism where human interaction is essential.

The literature on the language of tourism (Maci, 2013; Nigro, 2006; Spinzi, 2013) shows that this specialized discourse is full of cultural references, evocative and metaphorical expressions to create emotional connections while making persuasive appeals to different audiences. Rendering these subtle features across languages is a major challenge for tourism translation, as literal translations often struggle to capture the essence of the original message and align with the cultural expectations of the target audience. Tools driven by AI, such as neural machine translation (NMT), apply deep learning-based models to understand and translate complex linguistic constructs both precisely and fluently (Luong & Manning, 2015). While this approach has been successful, it has been pointed out that those tools struggle with figurative language—that is, metaphors, idioms, etc.—and also with region-specific expressions (Luong & Manning, 2015) that are important to create emotional resonance and ensure cultural authenticity (Pierini, 2007). This raises a dilemma of the extent to which AI can replicate creative techniques used by human translators (Hutchins, 2000).

The main aim of this study is therefore to investigate the opportunities and limitations of AI-driven metaphor translation. It builds on previous research on metaphor translation in the field of sustainable tourism (Spinzi, 2024), in which Dilts' (1983) model of Logical Levels was applied to metaphor interpretation in Italian and English languages and cultures. By combining quantitative and qualitative methods to identify and classify metaphors, Spinzi, (2024) shows that metaphors are often retained in the target language due to shared cultural or linguistic conventions between the two languages. More

specifically, the qualitative analysis reveals differences in cultural values and communication styles. In light of the identification of these metaphors, this study evaluates the relative efficiency of AI-driven methods compared to human translation when it comes to preserving the cultural and emotional subtleties of texts. In doing so, this research confirms the need to strike a balance between cultural authenticity and linguistic adaptability, thereby contributing to the discourse on the role of AI in addressing the complex demands of tourism translation. Ultimately, it assesses the extent to which AI can fulfil the twin goals of efficiency and cultural relevance in a field where human creativity and cultural awareness are essential.

2. Background

Empirical studies in the field of marketing and business (e.g., Burgers et al., 2015) have shown that both conventional and novel metaphors play a decisive role in shaping customer perceptions. This is due to the ability of metaphors to transform unfamiliar situations into familiar ones and to exert considerable persuasive power, which marketers often use strategically to influence people's thinking and behaviour. Research on the use of metaphors in tourism promotional discourse has confirmed the influence that tourism industry texts and images have on tourists' perceptions and decision-making behaviour, especially regarding their intentions to book trips, purchase travel packages or use tourism services (e.g., Chen & Tsai, 2007; Jaworska, 2017; Spinzi, 2024). Furthermore, in an age of widespread consumer culture where product differentiation is minimal, metaphors are used to facilitate the establishment of distinctive brands (Breeze, 2013).

In tourism discourse, metaphors rely primarily on embodiment to evoke physical, emotional and sensory responses that match the potential tourist's concrete engagement with the environment (see Spinzi, 2010; 2013). For example, a phrase such as 'the heart of Europe' is used in tourism discourses not only to describe a place, but also to give it qualities such as centrality, warmth and attraction (Jaworska, 2017). These fairly conventional metaphorical constructs are particularly effective in promotional materials as they condense complex ideas into vivid language that resonates with different audiences (Djafarova & Anderson, 2008; Gibbs, 2006). The importance of the cultural perspective in the study of metaphors has already been emphasised in the literature. It has been noted that (Kövecses, 2008) primary metaphors are generally universal, while complex metaphors are more specific in different languages. This observation highlights the dual nature of metaphors, which are both cognitively universal and cross-cultural, with variations across multiple dimensions, including social, regional, ethnic, stylistic, diachronic, and individual dimensions.

Briefly, metaphorical conceptualisation is determined by two primary factors: (1) embodiment, and (2) context. This stems from our endeavour to resonate with both physicality and culture. In other words, metaphors have their origin in our bodily experience, which all humans share and which can lead to metaphors that are universal because of this similarity. However, metaphors are not only shaped by bodily experience; they are also influenced by the cultural context in which they emerge. As a result, while some metaphors remain universally recognizable, others vary across cultures, reflecting distinct cultural perspectives while also exhibiting cross-cultural patterns.

The importance of context in the translation of metaphors in tourism is also emphasised by Stepins (2022), together with the linguistic and cultural characteristics and the communicative intentions of the source text. When it comes to translation techniques for rendering metaphors, the researcher suggests trying to maintain the same mapping scheme of the metaphor, i.e., the relationship between the source domain and the target domain. If this is not possible, an alternative conceptual mapping can be used. By adopting a cross-linguistic perspective, Stepins combines the linguistic and cognitive analysis of metaphor with the practical requirements of translation in the specific context of tourism discourse and provides with information regarding how to modify metaphors within a text in order to achieve a translation that sounds natural. This is accomplished by taking into account morphological differences and the context of the language being translated. All in all, translation trends in the use of metaphor reveal a complex interaction between preservation and adaptation strategies (Spinzi, 2024). The retention of most conventional metaphors alongside the decision to turn some into similes or render them non-figuratively illustrates translators' attempts to balance fidelity to the source text with cultural relevance and accessibility for the target audience.

As for the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on translation, AI has made considerable progress since its emergence in the mid-20th century, evolving from rule-based systems to complex neural architectures that mimic human perception and decision-making. The beginnings of AI in translation systems date back to the 1950s, when researchers began using computers for language translation. The first efforts were based on linguistic rules and dictionaries as the main sources of information. In the 1990s, the situation improved with the use of statistical machine translation (SMT), which was based on probabilistic models trained on large bilingual corpora to facilitate translation. Although SMT systems outperformed rule-based methods, they struggled to accurately transfer contextual and idiomatic details, especially for complex sentences (Luong & Manning, 2015). A major breakthrough came in the 2010s, when deep learning changed AI with the introduction of NMT. Unlike previous methods, NMT relies on artificial neural networks to process and create translations, drawing on extensive data sets and sophisticated learning

algorithms to achieve a refined understanding of language (Koehn, 2020). Indeed, NMT is able to dynamically adapt to linguistic nuances by training on parallel corpora. By acquiring knowledge from these environments, NMT systems are able to recognise subtle semantic relationships, idiomatic expressions and syntactic structures. Thanks to this contextual awareness, NMT can produce translations that are both grammatically correct and more coherent and fluent, accurately reflecting the natural flow of human language (Vaswani et al., 2017). According to Johnson et al. (2017), this innovation has established natural language translation (NMT) as the preeminent paradigm in modern machine translation systems. It has also formed the basis for widely used tools such as Google Translate and enabled significant advances in global communication and accessibility across cultural boundaries. Researchers have investigated methods to evaluate the effectiveness of AI models in translation. These include human evaluation, automated evaluation metrics and hybrid evaluation approaches. Although human evaluation is the costliest and labour-intensive, it is considered the most reliable method (Amini et al., 2024). In contrast, automated assessment metrics are less expensive but may not always agree with human assessment. Hybrid assessment methods attempt to combine the advantages of both approaches (Bojar et al., 2017).

Nevertheless, NMT systems are able to translate literal and simple language. However, their ability to interpret figurative expressions such as metaphors is limited by their lack of cultural and contextual awareness (Luong & Manning, 2015). The result is often either a literal translation that fails to convey the intended meaning or a neutralised version that does not resonate with the target audience. This is where AI meets Metaphor.

Advances in AI, including context-aware systems and models that integrate cultural datasets, offer the potential to improve metaphor translation by enabling systems to better understand figurative language and its cultural meaning (Vaswani et al., 2017). Furthermore, evaluating the quality of figurative language translations is complicated. Automated evaluation metrics may be insufficient in these cases to assess the suitability and fluency of the translation. Human judgment is still crucial for assessing the accuracy and quality of translations containing figurative language. Therefore, AI systems often need to be post-edited by humans to improve the translations of metaphors. This emphasises the importance of collaboration between technology and human translators to ensure accuracy and cultural relevance.

As Ripley (2021) explains, metaphors are understood by AI systems relying on NLP, based on the process of metaphor analysis, which aims at both metaphor identification—i.e., distinguishing between literal and metaphorical expressions—and interpretation—i.e., understanding the meaning of the metaphor in its context. The approach used is known as a slipnet, i.e., a kind of network that

establishes connections between domains. Paraphrasing, on the other hand, attempts to replace the verbs in the metaphorical expression and reinterpret them in a literal sense. In other words, AI uses NLP techniques to identify metaphors by finding the source and target expressions and then interpreting them through explanations that look for analogies or paraphrases that make the meaning more literal.

ChatGPT, the acronym for Generative Pre-Trained Transformer, uses self-attention mechanism of the Transformer architecture to interpret the relationships between words and their context (Vaswani et al., 2017). With the help of this mechanism, the model is able to evaluate and take into account the meaning of each token in relation to the other tokens contained in the same sentence. Conversation, writing, summarising and translating are all examples of natural language processing tasks that can be handled by this architecture. ChatGPT converts input words and phrases into numerical vectors called embeddings. These embeddings capture semantic and syntactic properties so that the system can recognise and match figurative language (Mikolov et al., 2013). By processing various linguistic data, the model can identify frequently used metaphors and their possible translations in different languages. Furthermore, ChatGPT employs its encoder-decoder architecture in translation to recontextualise metaphors while preserving their meaning in the target language (Wu et al., 2016). Although ChatGPT utilises advanced mechanisms, challenges related to cultural differences remain: Metaphors, as explained above, are strongly tied to culture and may not have direct equivalents (Kövecses, 2008). They are also context-dependent, which makes it difficult for the model to decide whether a literal or a figurative translation is appropriate (Jaworska, 2017). However, since ChatGPT utilises reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) to refine its ability to process complex expressions, including metaphors (Christiano et al., 2017), it can be observed that the feedback provided by users helps to improve the model's metaphor translation by directing it towards equivalents that are culturally appropriate and contextually correct.

3. Method

The main data set for the analysis comes from an Italian travel guide, *WeBeach Trebbia e Aveto*, published in 2020 by Filippo Tuccimei, and its translation into English. This guidebook, chosen for its metaphorical descriptions, highlights the sandy beaches of Trebbia amidst the breathtaking scenery of the Apennines and invites readers to discover waterfalls, dams and picturesque mediaeval villages on the cliffs of the river. The other dataset for the analysis comes from the translation of the Italian text created with OpenAI's GPT-4 architecture. The study applies a manual qualitative approach to evaluate and compare the handling of metaphors by AI and human translators. It builds on the

identification of metaphors in the Italian text and in the English TT conducted in previous research (Spinzi, 2024). The focus of this analysis is to compare the translated metaphors in the English TT with the same metaphors translated into English by ChatGTP. Both the AI translation and the human translation are evaluated according to the following aspects: (1) preservation of figurative meaning, i.e., assessment of whether the purpose and effect of the metaphor have been maintained, and (2) cultural adaptation, i.e., the extent to which the metaphor has been modified to fit the cultural context of the target language.

In order to verify whether the strategies used in the two translated texts are related to the main intention of the figurative language used, the metaphors identified in the ST are categorised according to the functions they fulfil in the tourism texts: descriptive, ideological, and aesthetic. When we talk about descriptive metaphors, we mean metaphors that help to clarify a concept, illustrate it or improve our understanding of it. The function of this type of metaphor is similar to the explanatory and modelling function proposed by Goatly (1997). A useful example is the metaphor of 'crystal clear water' which describes the natural water environment through a vivid visualisation that allows the reader to get a clearer picture of the landscape. Compared to other metaphors (e.g., aesthetic metaphors), descriptive metaphors place more emphasis on accuracy than poetic embellishment. For example, the aesthetic metaphor 'magical river', with its emotional resonance and appealing wording, encourages the audience to imagine sparkling waters, a calm environment or an ethereal atmosphere. In Italian language and culture in particular, these aesthetic metaphors, which are frequently used in Italian (Spinzi, 2010), tend to favour stylistic innovation at the expense of clarity or direct communication, as has been observed in literature. Finally, ideological metaphors are used to shape beliefs, influence attitudes and convey value-laden messages. The use of ideological metaphors can be interpreted as a method of constructing reality that contributes to maintaining or criticising power relations in society (Goatly, 1997). They are often found in political, social and cultural discourse to reinforce or challenge power structures. These metaphors aim to persuade or promote certain ideologies by embedding abstract concepts in familiar, emotionally charged images. An example of an ideological metaphor in ecotourism is the depiction of the environment as 'fragile' (Spinzi, 2010), as it characterises ecosystems as fragile and vulnerable entities that need to be carefully protected and managed. On a pragmatic level, the ideological metaphor is defined by its perlocutionary effect, i.e., it can inspire action in the real world (Maalej & Ning, 2011).

4. Analysis

The analysis begins with a classification of metaphors in the ST according to their main function: (1) descriptive, (2) aesthetic, or (3) ideological. It goes

without saying that the differences between these three functions are not clear-cut and the categorisation is usually based on the dominant function. The metaphor 'unspoilt nature', for example, is predominantly ideological, as it advocates the preservation of nature and sets the tone of the professional discourse on sustainability. It suggests that nature in its 'pristine' state is unspoilt and free from harmful human influences. It is an ideological framework that postulates an ecological ideal and contrasts the pristine with the state that has been spoilt or degraded by civilisation. Indeed, ecologism is an ideology that prioritises the preservation of ecosystems and recognises their fragility and need for protection. The metaphor implies that human intervention is often harmful and encourages us to reflect on our relationship with nature. It also contains poetic and descriptive elements that stimulate the reader's imagination with depictions of untamed and unspoilt places such as forests, crystal-clear rivers or deserted coastlines, ultimately highlighting the visual or physical qualities of the landscape. All occurrences of this metaphor have been faithfully translated in both texts, with the exception of two occurrences of 'raw nature' in the human-written translation. The use of 'raw nature' in example #1 refers to nature in its original, unprocessed state, emphasising its primitiveness and wildness. As mentioned elsewhere (Spinzi 2024), the 'deliberate' (Steen, 2017) use of 'raw' evokes the idea of something unprocessed or untamed and emphasises the primitive and unadulterated character of nature. The use of 'raw' is consistent with the precise textual context in which it occurs, in which a dichotomy between raw and refined nature is established. This contrast is not captured by the AI-supported interpretation, and all occurrences of the same metaphors are always translated with the epithets untouched or unspoiled.

Example #1

ST: Abbiamo promosso solo i corsi d'acqua che avessero determinate caratteristiche fisiche (apertura della valle e congrua esposizione al sole, portata d'acqua, profondità, adeguatezza della battigia, ecc.); abbiamo privilegiato quei corsi d'acqua (od i loro tratti) situati in valli scarsamente abitate, non inquinate e dominate dalla natura incontaminata; e quelle spiagge povere di elementi artificiali od architettonici, sposando con convinzione un concetto di turismo assolutamente verde, ricordando come troppo spesso il nostro mare sia stato piagato da un eccesso di costruzione delle sue coste.

TT: We selected only the rivers that had the right physical traits: an open valley and proper exposure to the sun, flow rate, depth, and the right kind of shore, etc. We embraced the concept of totally green tourism by giving priority to the parts of rivers located in scarcely-inhabited and

unpolluted valleys dominated by raw nature, and to the beaches without man-made elements or architectural structures.

AI: We have promoted only waterways with specific physical characteristics (valley openness and adequate sun exposure, water flow, depth, suitability of the shoreline, etc.); we prioritized those waterways (or their sections) located in sparsely inhabited, unpolluted valleys dominated by unspoiled nature; and those beaches with minimal artificial or architectural elements, fully embracing the concept of truly green tourism, while remembering how often our seas have been scarred by excessive coastal construction.

The second ideological and interesting metaphor that appears in the same passage compares the sea to a wounded or afflicted body, emphasising the damage caused by excessive coastal development. This is a powerful metaphor that evokes physical and emotional suffering and dramatises environmental degradation, prompting the reader to reflect on the consequences of human action. In the man-made translation, the metaphor is omitted. Instead of 'piagato/wounded', the TT shifts the focus away from the intended emotional and visual impact of the metaphor and concentrates on factual details that reduce the rhetorical weight. This omission diminishes the dramatic tone of the original text and distracts from the ST's emphasis on environmental degradation as a permanent wound to the sea. The metaphor is retained in the AI-assisted translation through the use of 'scarred', reflecting the symbolism of 'piagato' as a physical wound. This suggests that the rendering is more in line with the tone of the ST than the cultural orientations of English, which favour instrumental information over more expressive phrases (see Katan & Taibi, 2021). No omissions were found in the automatic translation of ideological metaphors.

Descriptive elements are crucial in tourism discourse as they vividly depict the environment to appeal to potential visitors. The translation choices of this group reflect decisions about cultural equivalence and audience engagement. In example #2, the river is personified and presented as if it can make the landscape more dynamic through its flow. The human-crafted translation is clear and comprehensible as it conveys the essential meaning, although the phrase 'makes a series of spectacular curves' diminishes the vividness of the ST by neglecting the implication of dynamic movement and the sequential aspect of the curves (e.g., spettacolari e consecutive curve vorticoso/spectacular and consecutive swirling curves). The tone of the translation sounds less suggestive than that of the original, and prioritises functionality over engagement. In contrast, the automatically generated phrase 'carves spectacular and successive whirling curves' mirrors the aesthetic and dynamic

language of the original very well and preserves its descriptive intent to the detriment of aesthetics.

Example #2

ST: In alcuni tratti il fiume **disegna spettacolari e consecutive curve vorticose**, la cui tipica espressione sono i c.d. Meandri di San Salvatore, dichiarati Sito di Importanza Comunitaria.

TT: In the extension from Marsaglia to San Salvatore, **the river makes a series of spectacular curves**, which are called the Meanders of San Salvatore, a declared Site of Community Importance.

AI: In certain sections, **the river carves spectacular and consecutive swirling curves**, exemplified by the so-called Meanders of San Salvatore, designated as a Site of Community Importance.

The AI-generated translation is more faithful to the style of the original text, but occasionally omits ideologically significant content or introduces deviations in tone. The following example, where the aesthetic function of the metaphor dominates, illustrates this deviation once again:

Example #3

ST: Il guado viene normalmente praticato dalla gente ma, nelle giornate più affollate, può garantire una solitudine da **"atollo."**

TT: The ford is used quite often, and on crowded days it can get you to a **deserted-island like place of solitude.**

AI: The ford is commonly used by people, but on busier days, it can still offer solitude reminiscent of an **"atoll."**

By comparing the ford to the quiet seclusion of an atoll, the formulation 'solitudine da atollo' evokes feelings of peace and seclusion. The sentence structure creates a subtle juxtaposition between the ford's ability to offer solitude and its general use. Using the metaphor 'atollo' the text expresses its meaning succinctly and poetically. In line with the English culture, the human translator has adapted the text by providing a simile that is more accessible. The AI translation clearly preserves the poetic style of the ST and enhances the rendering through the deliberate use of the word 'reminiscent' which adds an extra layer of sophistication. The choice of translation here has a significant impact on how the lyrical quality of the text is conveyed. Apart from the example above, another metaphor 'la sinfonia della natura incontaminata', which is completely omitted in the TT, is literally rendered as 'the symphony of untouched nature' in the automatic translation. The AI translation restores

the aesthetic metaphor omitted in the TT and emphasises the harmonious and untouched qualities of nature. This emphasises the potential of the AI translation to better preserve the lyrical elements of the ST in comparison to the TT.

5. Discussion

Significant differences in terms of fidelity to the original text, cultural adaptation and readability are worth discussing. As we can infer from the renditions in Appendix A—which shows the most frequent metaphors in the data and the main differences between the AI-generated text and human-based translations when rendering metaphors in tourism discourse—AI tends to translate metaphors literally or poetically retaining the rhetorical effect of the original text. While this approach ensures greater stylistic fidelity (e.g., No. 15 the ‘symphony’), it can also make the text less natural or less suitable for the target audience. The human translator, on the other hand, adopts a strategy that is more focused on clarity and functionality (e.g., No. 4: push your way through a bunch of people just to get yourself a square foot). He intervenes in the metaphors to make them more accessible to the target reader, even at the cost of simplifying or omitting them (19% of cases of omission in the TT). This tendency is particularly evident in ideological metaphors, where the AI retains expressions with a strong emotional impact, while the human translation softens them or rephrases them in a more neutral way. In descriptive metaphors, the AI also emphasises suggestive aspects by adding qualifiers, while the human translator prefers a more concise and functional rendering. Finally, for aesthetic metaphors, AI is characterised by its ability to recreate lyrical images that are often omitted by human translators, helping to preserve the suggestive dimension of the original text (e.g., scarred). The results show clear strengths and weaknesses of TT and automatic translation approaches. While TT often comes close to meeting audience expectations by clarifying or amplifying elements, it sometimes sacrifices the poetic or stylistic nuances of ST. In contrast, AI-generated translation often adds additional qualifiers that enhance the vividness of the description. Even if comprehension is maintained, the frequent use of appealing words can occasionally lead to redundancy.

These observations have significant implications for the tourism sector, where figurative language plays a crucial role in the perception of destinations. Maintaining metaphorical subtleties is essential in cross-cultural communication; as such, language not only enriches the appeal of a destination but also expresses its cultural identity. Failure to retain these subtleties due to overly literal human translations or inflexible AI output jeopardises cultural interpretation and reduces emotional resonance, ultimately undermining the effectiveness of promotional materials.

This analysis shows that while AI systems have significant advantages in terms of speed, consistency and structural integrity, they lack the cultural and emotional depth required for creative copy, such as tourism promotion. Consequently, improving AI tools is essential, particularly by incorporating culturally specific datasets and optimising NMT algorithms to process metaphorical and evocative language more effectively.

AI allows for the analysis of large amounts of data to understand individual customer preferences and behaviors, enabling companies in the sector to offer personalized evocative messages and recommendations. LLMs can create customized travel itineraries, suggest activities, help to describe attractive destinations through figurative language, and accommodations tailored to travelers' preferences, past behaviors, and current trends. Sentiment analysis, through natural language processing techniques, helps companies classify feedback as positive, negative, or neutral (cf. Kovecses, 2023). Thematic analysis, through AI, identifies recurring themes and metaphorical patterns in customer feedback, uncovering important issues and trends for customers. Text analysis combines NLP with machine learning algorithms to analyze unstructured textual data from customer reviews, extracting useful information such as emerging trends, common complaints, and positive aspects.

6. Conclusion

AI can surely be used to overcome language barriers in all the intense communication in the tourism industry. It can certainly be used to translate all the documents into different languages and thus accelerate the communication machine of the tourism industry. It is effective and quick in overcoming language barriers; however, when it comes to cultural references, human intervention is crucial.

Therefore, AI should be seen as a complementary tool that supports the human translator by automating monotonous tasks and ensuring structural coherence so that the human can focus on improving the cultural and emotional aspects of the text. This collaborative method would optimise the benefits of both AI and human skills and ensure that translations meet the complex requirements of the tourism sector.

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Appendix A: Categorization of the most frequent metaphors in the corpus

		Source Text	Target Text	AI Translation
1	Ideological	il nostro mare sia stato piagato	<i>Omission</i>	scarred by excessive coastal construction
2	Ideological	la natura regna sovrana	nature reigns supreme	nature dominates majestically
3	Descriptive	completamente immersa nella natura	total immersion in nature	totally surrounded by nature
4	Descriptive	guadagnare un metro quadrato di spiaggia	push your way through a bunch of people just to get yourself a square foot	Another strength of the beaches featured here: you won't have to elbow your way through the crowd to claim a square meter of beach!
5	Descriptive	Il torrente il cui letto, anche in presenza di spiaggia sabbiosa, è solitamente tappezzato di sassi e sassetti;	<i>Omission</i>	The stream, whose bed, even when featuring a sandy beach, is usually covered with stones and pebbles;
6	Descriptive	le acque cristalline	the crystal-clear waters	the transparent and pristine waters
7	Descriptive	incastonato l'abitato di San Salvatore	the village of San Salvatore is nestled	the village of San Salvatore is embedded
8	Descriptive	le trasparenze caraibiche	Caribbean-like waters	waters reminiscent of the Caribbean
9	Descriptive	una riva vergine	an untouched shore	a pristine riverside
10	Descriptive	un tuffo nella storia	a dive into history	an immersion in history
11	Aesthetic	un paesaggio da fiaba	a fairytale landscape	a storybook setting
12	Aesthetic	un luogo incantato	an enchanted place	a magical spot
13	Aesthetic	Una solitudine da 'atollo'	a deserted-island like place of solitude	solitude reminiscent of an 'atoll'
14	Aesthetic	un piccolo Eden	a small Eden	a little paradise
15	Aesthetic	la sinfonia della natura incontaminata	<i>Omission</i>	the symphony of untouched nature
16	Aesthetic	andando ad infrangersi sulla rupe	as it crashes against the cliff	as it breaks upon the cliff